

Deliverable 6.3

Project ID	654241
Project Title	A comprehensive and standardised e-infrastructure for analysing medical metabolic phenotype data
Project Acronym	PhenoMeNal
Start Date of the Project	1st September 2015
Duration of the Project	36 Months
Work Package Number	6
Work Package Title	PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community Gateway
Deliverable Title	D6.3 Online user feedback form
Delivery Date	M12
Work Package leader	EMBL-EBI
Contributing Partners	EMBL-EBI
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Abstract: User feedback in one of the most important ways to improve user satisfaction and ensure our offering is fit for purpose. With the integration of an automated ticketing system, we have a powerful tool to manage user requests.	

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

User feedback is one of the most important ways to improve user satisfaction and ensure our offering is fit for purpose. Just collecting feedback does not make our users more satisfied; we need to make sure our users feel the benefit of their feedback. Together with the current on-going User Experience (UX) activities, in addition to the extensive UX work already carried out in D6.1 (User Experience Document on VRC Design Guide), user feedback will continue to be very important in our future development. We specifically acknowledge the importance of structured user feedback forms, i.e. capturing categories of issues and priority indicators, in order to efficiently delegate issues to the experts most suitable to tackle a specific user problem in a timely manner.

We have chosen to implement a Wordpress plugin to capture and manage all user feedback. The feedback form is available at <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/help/>

2. CONTRIBUTION TOWARDS PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- Task 6.2: Deployment of the PhenoMeNal VRC.
- D6.3 Online user feedback form. As part of the VRE deployment we included the user feedback component.

3. DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE

Constructive feedback, bug reporting and feature request will help drive the development of the PhenoMeNal general website, VRE and the tools therein. The PhenoMeNal website and VRE is currently running in the public cloud of EMBL-EBI.

With the obvious benefits of running an established Document Management System (DMS), we decided to use WordPress¹ for the general website. WordPress has a large number of plugins² available. After comparing features and evaluating the maturity of existing offerings, we chose an advanced plugin called “WP Support Plus”³. At the time of our decision this was clearly the most used free option for WordPress, which

aided our final choice and also ensured sustainability and continuity after the initial funding stages.

The main WP Support Plus (WPS) functionality that we are currently using for efficient issue tracking and scheduling include:

- User ticket prioritising and tracking (Figure 1)
- Categorisation of requests
- Allocation of tickets to relevant consortium members (agents) (Figure 2)
- Integration to automatically add new tasks into our shared project management tool Pivotal Tracker (Figure 3)

Current feedback/support categories are:

- **General.** For general enquires about the project and website
- **Tools.** Enquiries about the Metabolomics tools available through the VRE
- **Information.** Requests for further information
- **Partners.** Enquiries to or about project partners
- **Feedback.** Feedback not related to issues or enquiries
- **Feature request.** Ask for new features in website, VRE and appliances available within the VRE
- **Bug Reporting.** When a user encounter a problem/bug

This is by no means an exhaustive list, as the categorisation will be reviewed in the future when more tickets have been reported.

Any user or registered member can fill in the feedback form at <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/help/>. Administrators (agents) can also reply, delegate and generally administer the tickets from the same page (Figure 2) after having logged in with the correct credentials.

Create New Ticket [FAQs](#)

Contact us
E-mail: phenomenal-help@ebi.ac.uk

Name *

Email Address *

Subject *

Description *

B I U S x₂ x² I_x

Styles Normal Font Size Source

I am interested in your work and I would like to look at the source code for the PhenoMeNal project, where can I find it?

body p

Category *

Priority *

Figure 1. User feedback form as seen from a user perspective. Users have to supply all fields requested, and the suggestion/issue is simply described in free-text. The information captured here will go to the referenced email distribution list as well as automatically being added into our project management task tracker tool (Pivotal Tracker)

ID	Status	Subject	Raised By	Type	Category	Assigned to	Priority	Updated
11	Open	Automated integratio...	Ken Haug	Guest	Information	None	Low	5 minutes ago
9	Open	New version of Suppo...	Kenneth Haug	User	Information	Namrata	Medium	1 hours ago
2	Closed	Is the feedback form...	Kenneth Haug	Guest	General	Kenneth Haug	High	1 hours ago
6	Closed	External request	Steffen Neumann	Guest	Feedback	Pablo Moreno	Low	1 hours ago
10	Open	Where can I find the...	Kenneth Haug	Guest	Feedback	Pablo Moreno	Medium	1 hours ago

Figure 2. Example screenshot of the ticketing system. This is the view we as administrators get and offers the ability to allocate, filter and prioritise tasks to PhenoMeNal consortia members.

PhenoMeNal-H2020 <phenomenal.h2020@gmail.com> - [Ticket Phnmnl#11] Automated integration with Pivotal is now set up

ID #126491793 <https://www.pivotaltracker.com/story/show/126491> Close

STORY TYPE ★ Feature

POINTS 1 Point

STATE Start Unscheduled

REQUESTER AUT PhenoMeNal

OWNERS KH NK +

FOLLOW THIS STORY (3 followers)

Updated: less than a minute ago

DESCRIPTION (edit)

Ken Haug (kenneth@ebi.ac.uk) wrote:
Use email "phenomenal.tzqtw@zapiemail.com" to automatically create new stories in our Pivotal Tracker

LABELS

automated supportcall

TASKS

Add a task Add

ACTIVITY

KH **Kenneth Haug** @khaug

Add a comment

📎 📍 👤 🗨️ cancel Add

Figure 3. Example screenshot of the Pivotal Tracker integration. This shows an example of how a task will look after automatically being integrated into Pivotal Tracker.

4. WORK PLAN

4.1. Structure and management of WP6 Tasks

As with the rest of the project, WP6 is managed with the help of a Pivotal Tracker project. Online documents (Google Documents) combined with online calls (Google Hangout) enable a free collaborative work environment, and also play a key role in the managing all work packages in the project.

Figure 4. Report of all WP6 tasks in the PhenoMeNal Pivotal Tracker project, as per mid July 2016. This is one of many report we can generate from Pivotal Tracker. Please note that this view is in terms of predicted work effort and is not related to time to completion.

Utilization of resources for current deliverable:

Partner	Total PM
EMBL-EBI	0.25

5. DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

The deliverable was submitted on time.

6. CONCLUSION

The PhenoMeNal consortium now has an effective sustainable feedback tool that enables us to act upon requests in a personalised manner. In addition, by integrating WP Support Plus feedback forms with our Pivotal Tracker project management tool we can rapidly allocate suitable consortia users to deal with the request as they happen.

7. References

1. <https://wordpress.com>
2. <https://wordpress.org/plugins/>
3. <https://wordpress.org/plugins/wp-support-plus-responsive-ticket-system/>